

Optimal phase matching for second harmonic generation in monoclinic non-linear optical crystals determined by extreme surfaces method

Oleh Buryy

Department of Semiconductor Electronics
Lviv Polytechnic National University
Lviv, Ukraine
oleh.a.buryi@lpnu.ua

Andriy Danylov

Department of Applied Physics and Nanomaterials
Science
Lviv Polytechnic National University
Lviv, Ukraine
andanylov@yahoo.com

Anatoliy Andrushchak

Department of Applied Physics and Nanomaterials
Science
Lviv Polytechnic National University
Lviv, Ukraine
anatolii.s.andrushchak@lpnu.ua

Bouchta Sahraoui

Institute of Sciences and Molecular Technologies of Angers
University of Angers
Angers, France
bouchta.sahraoui@univ-angers.fr

Abstract – The optimal phase matching is determined for the second harmonic generation (SHG) in biaxial non-linear optical crystals of monoclinic symmetry – BiBO, LCB (point group 2), GdCOB, YCOB (point group m). For the case of vector phase matching, the directions of wave vectors of input and output beams corresponding to the highest possible SHG efficiency are determined by the extreme surfaces method. It is shown, that the use of vector phase matching allows to increase the SHG efficiency on a value about a few percent for the considered crystals.

Keywords – second harmonic generation; monoclinic crystals; interaction geometry; extreme surfaces.

I. INTRODUCTION

As it is known, the effect of second harmonic generation (SHG) in non-linear optical media is widely used to obtain coherent light with wavelength shorter than the one of initial source both in bulk crystals and nanocomposites [1–4]. The efficiency of SHG in crystals strongly depends on the directions of pump (initial) and second harmonic (output) beams. Determination of optimal directions poses no difficulties for uniaxial non-linear optical crystals and scalar phase matching (PM), when the directions of input and output beams coincide [5]. The analysis of scalar PM in biaxial crystals is much more complex [6–13]; the general case of vector phase matching in biaxial crystals, to our knowledge, not yet analyzed. Here we present the solution of this problem by extreme surfaces method previously used for the analysis of vector PM in uniaxial crystals [14,15] as well as for determination of optimal geometries of induced optical effects in crystals (see, e.g. [16–19] and the papers cited in them). Here we restrict our analysis by monoclinic crystals because the orthorhombic ones are considered in [20] (although SHG was revealed or expected to

be revealed in a number of biaxial organic crystals of triclinic symmetry [21–24], they are not used in optical devices and there is no information about their non-linear susceptibilities).

II. BASIC RELATIONS

As well as in [14,15], we consider the dependence of the SHG efficiency on the directions of the light beams. In this case, for simplicity, only the geometrical factor of the efficiency is taken into account:

$$\eta = \frac{(\vec{e}_3 \hat{d} \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_2)^2}{n_1(\lambda_p) n_2(\lambda_p) n_3(\lambda_{SH})}, \quad (1)$$

where \hat{d} is the tensor of non-linear susceptibility, λ_p is the pump beams wavelength, λ_{SH} is SH beam wavelength, $\lambda_{SH} = 0.5 \cdot \lambda_p$, $n_1(\lambda_p)$, $n_2(\lambda_p)$, $n_3(\lambda_{SH})$ are the refraction indices of pump (p) and second harmonic (SH) beams, for scalar PM $n_1(\lambda_p) = n_2(\lambda_p)$, \vec{e}_1 , \vec{e}_2 , \vec{e}_3 are the unit vectors parallel to the electric vectors of the corresponding waves, $\vec{e}_j \sim \hat{\epsilon} \vec{i}_j$, $\hat{\epsilon}$ is the tensor of dielectric permittivity, \vec{i}_j is the unit vector of electric displacement (or light wave polarization) determined for the each direction of the wave vector \vec{k} in a known manner [5].

The expression (1) was used for the construction of the extreme surfaces representing the highest achievable values of η for all possible directions of the output wave vector \vec{k}_3 , determined by the angles θ , φ of the spherical coordinate system. At that for each direction of \vec{k}_3 we searched such directions of $\vec{k}_{1,2}$ which maximize the value of η . This value determines the absolute value of the radius-vector of extreme

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surface, whereas its direction coincides with the one of \vec{k}_3 . It also should be taken into account, that the highest SH efficiency is achieved if the phase matching condition is realized. In the general case of vector PM it is written as:

$$\vec{k}_3 = \vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2. \quad (2)$$

For scalar PM this condition transforms to the one between the absolute values of the wave vectors, $k_3 = k_1 + k_2$.

Generally, for each direction in non-cubic crystal two light waves with orthogonal polarizations can propagate. In the case of biaxial crystal the lengths of the wave vectors of these waves $k = |\vec{k}|$ are determined from the equation [5]:

$$k^4 (K_1^2 m_1^2 + K_2^2 m_2^2 + K_3^2 m_3^2) - k (K_1^2 (K_2^2 + K_3^2) m_1^2 + K_2^2 (K_1^2 + K_3^2) m_2^2 + K_3^2 (K_1^2 + K_2^2) m_3^2) + K_1^2 K_2^2 K_3^2 = 0, \quad (3)$$

where K_1, K_2, K_3 are the lengths of wave vectors along crystallographic axes, $K_i = 2\pi N_i / \lambda$, N_i is the main refraction indices, $i = 1, 2, 3$, m_1, m_2, m_3 are the components of the wave normal. The equation (3) describes the double-cavity wave vector surface (Fig. 1). The external part of this surface corresponds to a 'slow' (*s*) wave characterized by higher value of the refraction index n and, consequently, by lower value of speed of light and higher absolute value of the wave vector, $k = 2\pi n / \lambda$. Contrary, the internal part of this surface corresponds to a 'fast' (*f*) wave. For biaxial crystals, the PM condition (2) can be satisfied in two possible cases: (i) both pump waves are slow (*ssf* or type I phase matching) or (ii) one pump wave is slow and the other is fast (*sff* or type II phase matching) [3] (the output wave is fast in both cases).

Fig. 1. One-eighth part of the wave vector surface for the case of biaxial crystal.

The consideration of vector PM is significantly complicated by the fact that, for each direction of \vec{k}_3 , the PM condition (2) can be satisfied for different directions of \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2 (Fig. 2). Generally, different values of the efficiency η correspond to different \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2 (for the same \vec{k}_3). To determine the maximal

of them, η_{max} , the values of η should be calculated for all \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2 (certainly, with some small enough step) forming the cone in Fig. 2. At that all possible vectors \vec{k}_1 are finished and all possible vectors \vec{k}_2 are started from the line *C* which points can be determined in the following way. Let the wave vector \vec{k}_3 is known and, for certainty, the type I (*ssf*) PM is considered. In this case both wave vectors \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2 are finished at the external part of the wave vector surface. Let shift the surface corresponding to the wave vector \vec{k}_2 from the origin to the end of the wave vector \vec{k}_3 . Now the surfaces for the wave vectors \vec{k}_1 and \vec{k}_3 intersect along the closed line *C* each point of which corresponds to the ends of vectors \vec{k}_1 and $\vec{k}_3 + \vec{k}_2$ (if this intersection is absent, PM can not be achieved for considered wavelengths and/or type of phase matching). Because the inversion of the wave vector \vec{k}_2 does not change the polarizations of light beams, this line corresponds to the condition (2). In our analysis the Dragilev' method was used for the determination of this line. This method was used in our papers dedicated to searching of the global maxima of the acousto-optic effect in crystals [16,17]. It allows to consistently calculate the coordinates of points of the line; this, in turn, is necessary to determine the values of η along it.

Fig. 2. The mutual position of the wave vectors of pump and SH beams.

If the maximal efficiency η_{max} was determined for all possible SH wave vector directions ($\theta=0 \dots \pi, \varphi=0 \dots 2\pi$), the global maximal value of the efficiency η_{max}^{extr} can be obtained as the highest value from the set of the values of η_{max} determined for all \vec{k}_3 . The dependence $\eta_{max}(\theta, \varphi)$ is conveniently presented as a 3D surface (the extreme one in accordance with the method of its calculation). Here we construct such surfaces and determine the optimal PM conditions for monoclinic non-linear optical crystals BiB_3O_6 (BiBO), $\text{La}_2\text{CaB}_{10}\text{O}_{19}$ (LCB), $\text{GdCa}_4\text{O}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ (GdCOB), $\text{YCa}_4\text{O}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ (YCOB) which parameters are given in Table 1. The values of the parameters were taken from [25, 26], in particular, the refraction indices were calculated in accordance with Sellmeier equations given

BiBO

LCB

GdCOB

YCOB

Fig. 3. Extreme surfaces $\eta_{max}(\theta, \varphi)$ for vector phase matching in monoclinic non-linear optical crystals (in pm^2/V^2).

Generally, the use of vector PM does not allow to increase significantly the efficiency η in comparison with the case of scalar PM: the highest relative increase κ takes place for *sff* PM in BiBO crystal, but even in this case it is only about 6%. For *ssf* PM in GdCOB the maximal achievable value of the efficiency η obtained for vector PM coincides with the one obtained for scalar PM. Almost the same situation occurs for *sff* PM in LCB and YCOB: the relative increase κ for them is less than one percent (0.6% and 0.3% correspondingly). It should be noted, that this result is very different from that obtained for uniaxial [14,15] and biaxial orthorhombic [20] crystals, where the relative increase κ could reach hundreds or even thousands of percent.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The optimal geometries of vector phase matching, i.e. the optimal directions of wave vectors of input (pump) and output (second harmonic) beams are determined by extreme surfaces method for second harmonic generation in biaxial non-linear optical crystals of monoclinic symmetry – BiBO, LCB, GdCOB, YCOB. Both first (*ssf*) and second (*sff*) type phase matching were considered. As it is shown, the highest achievable SHG efficiencies for vector PM are practically the same as the ones for scalar PM in the cases of LCB (*sff*), GdCOB (*ssf*) and YCOB (*sff*) crystals. Besides, the *sff* PM is absent in GdCOB at the considered wavelength of initial beams (1.0642 μm). For the case of *ssf* phase matching in LCB and YCOB the relative increase is equal to 1.6% and 3.6% correspondingly. The highest increase among the considered crystals was revealed for BiBO: 4.5% for *ssf* and 6.1% for *sff* phase matching.

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